

Dirac Particle in Newman–Unti–Tamburino Spacetime

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(Received 02 September, 2025)

We derive the Dirac equation in the background of the Newman–Unti–Tamburino (NUT) spacetime by applying the tetrad formalism, and separate the angular and radial parts. We get the system of two differential equations for angular functions and solve them in terms of hypergeometric functions. Then a NUT-charge dependent quantization rule for the angular separation constant has been established. As a result of studying the radial equations, we demonstrate that the probability of particle-antiparticle production on the outer event horizon decreases with the increase of the NUT charge. For the massless fermion, we construct the solution of the radial system of Dirac equation in terms of the confluent Heun functions that allows to get the NUT-charge dependent scattering resonances. Under the assumption of small NUT charge, we study the extremal NUT black hole with a single horizon, when the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy vanishes identically, and reveal the non-zero NUT charge effects in wave characteristics.

PACS numbers: 02.30.Gp, 02.40.Ky, 03.65.Ge, 04.62.+v

Keywords: Riemannian geometry, Newman–Unti–Tamburino spacetime, Dirac equation, spin 1/2 particle, NUT charge

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19346806>

1. Introduction

Newman–Unti–Tamburino (NUT) metrics have been determined as a vacuum solution of Einstein equations and generalize the Schwarzschild metric due to the presence of an additional parameter called the NUT parameter or the NUT charge [1–3]. Currently, the testing of the NUT charge effects in the spectra of quasars, supernovae, or active galactic nuclei is one of the striking problems of modern cosmology [4] as the black holes with NUT metric are considered to be physically meaningful systems with some special characteristics. Due to axial symmetry, the black holes with NUT charge may exhibit some effects similar to the Kerr black holes, such as asymmetry of black hole shadow or the Lense–Thirring effect [3, 5]. In [6], it has been shown from the thermodynamical

analysis that the observable mass of black hole is modified by the NUT parameter. Besides this, when introducing the NUT parameter in an anti-de-Sitter metric the appearance of a region with the negative Gibbs free energy in thermodynamics of black holes occurs, that is associated with the 1st-order phase transition[7].

A problem of two interacting Bogomol'nyi–Prasad–Sommerfield monopoles may be geometrized, and then reduced to finding geodesics in configuration space of the Taub-NUT type [8]. By this reason, the NUT metric has been actively studied as a monopole-like solution within the grand unified theories. A Kaluza–Klein monopole has been considered as a Taub-NUT gravitational instanton in the so-called Euclidean Taub-NUT five-dimensional (5D) manifold [9]. In such a 5D model, a Dirac problem has the specific Kaluza–Klein term which couples the spin with a magnetic field as in the Schrödinger–Pauli nonrelativistic theory. In [10], the Maxwell equations in a four-dimensional (4D) Taub-NUT space were solved within the Newman–Penrose formalism. The Dirac equation

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in the 4D Taub-NUT space was considered in the paper [11]. However, due a loss of Hamiltonian diagonalization at variable separation in [11], the obtained radial system of two equations is incorrect.

In [12], it has been shown that the Taub-NUT metrics may be obtained from the general class of asymptotically flat metrics by choosing a gauge field as corresponding to the Dirac magnetic monopole. In other words, the Dirac monopole generates a family of Taub-NUT solutions. Other members of this family could correspond to stationary Weyl solutions with the axial symmetry and a non-trivial NUT charge.

The NUT charge is referred to as a gravitomagnetic monopole and interpreted as a linear source of a pure angular momentum [3]. Two left and right twists remain the chiral symmetry of the Universe with Taub-NUT metric. However, up to day the experimental cosmology does not confirm the existence of indefinitely small difference between left- and right-handed twisting at latest stages of Universe evolution [13].

Baryon asymmetry arises during the first-order phase transition in Early Universe. The asymmetry of the left and right twists in a NUT metric may be a source of the origin of the baryon asymmetry. The original 4D NUT metric attracted not so much attention of the scientific community. The situation changes in recent years. Geodesics in NUT spacetimes were studied extensively [14–16]. However, a twisted quantum-mechanical motion of Dirac particle has been not explored.

It should be noted that many different approaches exist for the Dirac equation, even in Minkowski space. In this connection see, for instance, the detailed reviews are given in [17, 18]. In this paper, when working with the Dirac equation in NUT-space, we will use the conventional tetrad method developed by Tetrode–Weyl–Fock–Ivanenko in [19–22]. The Newman–Penrose approach [23] will be utilized also for finding a null tetrad.

Our goal is to examine the quantum-mechanical problem of a spin 1/2 particle in the background of the original NUT metric,

to construct analytical solutions of angular and radial systems derived after separating the variables in Dirac equation, and to investigate impact of the NUT charge on the scattering process.

2. The NUT metric model

The family of NUT metrics is defined by the line element

$$ds^2 = \Phi (dt - Wd\phi)^2 - \frac{dr^2}{\Phi} - (a^2 + r^2) (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\Phi = 1 - \frac{r_g r + 2a^2}{r^2 + a^2} = \frac{\Delta}{\rho^2}, \quad W = 2a(\cos \theta + C).$$

Here a designates NUT parameter, r_g is a Schwarzschild radius. The value of the constant C distinguishes between two main cases:

1) the original NUT-metric at

$$C = -1, \quad W = -4a \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2}; \quad (2.2)$$

2) the Taub-NUT metric at

$$C = 0, \quad W = 2a \cos \theta. \quad (2.3)$$

These two cases describe different geometries: the original NUT-metric has the only one singularity at $\theta = \pi$, and the Taub-NUT metric involves singularities at semi-infinite axes $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi$. From the physical point of view, this two cases should correspond to different physical sources of NUT-metrics.

Further we employ the original NUT-metric (2.2); the metric tensor reads

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \begin{vmatrix} \Phi & 0 & 0 & V \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{\Phi} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -S & 0 \\ V & 0 & 0 & \frac{V^2}{\Phi} - S \sin^2 \theta \end{vmatrix}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $V = 2a\Phi(1 - \cos \theta)$ and $S = a^2 + r^2$. We

chose the following tetrad

$$e_{(a)\alpha}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi & 0 & 0 & 2a\Phi^{\frac{1}{2}}(1 - \cos\theta) \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\Phi^{\frac{1}{2}}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S^{\frac{1}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S^{\frac{1}{2}}\sin\theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.5)$$

Applying the known formulas [24]

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{abc} &= \frac{1}{2}(\lambda_{abc} + \lambda_{bca} - \lambda_{cab}), \\ \lambda_{abc} &= \left(\frac{\partial e_{(a)\alpha}}{\partial x^\beta} - \frac{\partial e_{(a)\beta}}{\partial x^\alpha} \right) e_{(b)}^\alpha e_{(c)}^\beta, \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

we calculate the Ricci rotation coefficients as

$$\gamma_{ab0} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{\Phi'}{2\sqrt{\Phi}} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\Phi'}{2\sqrt{\Phi}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma_{ab1} = 0,$$

$$\gamma_{ab2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{r\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{r\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\gamma_{ab3} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -\frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{r\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} \\ \frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\tan\theta\sqrt{S}} \\ 0 & -\frac{r\sqrt{\Phi}}{S} & -\frac{1}{\tan\theta\sqrt{S}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

3. A tetrad formalism

The Dirac equation in the curved space has the form [19–22]

$$[i\gamma^\alpha(x) (\partial_\alpha + \Gamma_\alpha(x)) - M] \Psi(x) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

where

$$\Gamma_\alpha(x) = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^{ab} e_{(a)}^\beta e_{(b)\beta;\alpha} \text{ is the spinor connection,}$$

$$\gamma^\alpha(x) = \gamma^a e_{(a)}^\alpha(x), \quad \sigma^{ab} = \frac{1}{4}(\gamma^a\gamma^b - \gamma^b\gamma^a),$$

; α denote covariant derivative; M is a Dirac particle mass. The equation (3.1) can be presented with the use of the Ricci rotation coefficients $\gamma_{abc}(x) = -\gamma_{bac} = e_{(b)\beta;\alpha} e_{(a)}^\beta e_{(c)}^\alpha$ as follows [24]:

$$\left[i\gamma^c \left(e_{(c)}^\alpha \partial_\alpha + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^{ab}\gamma_{abc} \right) - M \right] \Psi = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

Apply the multiplication rule for three Dirac matrices

$$\gamma^c\gamma^a\gamma^b = \gamma^c g^{ab} - \gamma^a g^{cb} + \gamma^b g^{ca} + i\gamma^5 \epsilon^{cabk} \gamma_k,$$

$$\gamma^5 = -i\gamma^0\gamma^1\gamma^2\gamma^3, \quad \epsilon^{0123} = +1,$$

we get

$$\gamma^c\sigma^{ab} = \frac{1}{2}(g^{ca}\gamma^b - g^{cb}\gamma^a + i\gamma^5 \epsilon^{cabk} \gamma_k).$$

Taking the last expression into account, the Dirac equation (3.1) takes the form

$$\left[i\gamma^k (e_{(k)}^\alpha \partial_\alpha + \frac{1}{2}e_{(k);\alpha}^\alpha - \frac{i}{4}\gamma^5 \epsilon_k^{abc} \gamma_{abc}) - M \right] \Psi(x) = 0. \quad (3.3)$$

With introducing the notations

$$B_k(x) = \frac{1}{2} e_{(k);\alpha}^\alpha(x), \quad C_k(x) = \frac{1}{4} \epsilon^{abc}{}_k \gamma_{abc}(x)$$

the Dirac equation reads

$$\left[i\gamma^k (e_{(k)}^\alpha \partial_\alpha + B_k - i\gamma^5 C_k) - M \right] \Psi(x) = 0, \quad (3.4)$$

where $B(x)$ and $C(x)$ are vector-potential and pseudo-vector potentials of a gravitomagnetic field.

Further, we will demonstrate that there exist space-time regions with null (isotropic) tetrad, where the gravitomagnetic potential behaves similar to a gravitational field.

From 12 Newman–Penrose spin coefficients [25] only the following 4 coefficients are nonzero ones:

$$\lambda = \gamma_{133} = n_{i;j} \bar{m}^i \bar{m}^j = \frac{r\sqrt{\Phi}}{r^2 + a^2},$$

$$-\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_{100} - \gamma_{320}) = \frac{1}{2}(l_{i;j}m^i l^j - m_{i;j}\bar{m}^i l^j) = \frac{1}{2}\left(-\frac{\Phi'}{2\sqrt{\Phi}} + \frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{r^2 + a^2}\right),$$

$$-\alpha = \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{233} = \frac{1}{2}(l_{i;j}n^i \bar{m}^j - m_{i;j}\bar{m}^i \bar{m}^j) = \frac{1}{2 \tan \theta \sqrt{r^2 + a^2}},$$

$$-\rho = \gamma_{203} = l_{i;j}\bar{m}^i l^j = \frac{a\sqrt{\Phi}}{r^2 + a^2},$$

where n, l, m, \bar{m} are null orthogonal vectors, the bar denotes the complex conjugation.

Let assume the restrictions $|a^2| > 1, r^2 < 1, rr_g < 1$, when $\sqrt{\Phi} = \pm iP \rightarrow \pm i, \Phi' \rightarrow 0$. We suppose that $m^i = iT^i, \bar{m}^j = -iT^j, T^i$ are real functions. One can make a substitution $n = \pm iN, l = \pm iL$, here N is real, while L is a complex-valued function. Then one gets that

$$\lambda = \pm(-i)N_{i;j}T^i T^j = \pm \frac{ir}{r^2 + a^2},$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2}T_{i;j}T^i(\pm iL^j) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pm ia}{r^2 + a^2},$$

$$\alpha = \frac{i}{2}(T_{i;j}T^i T^j + (\pm L_{i;j}N^i T^j)) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pm 1}{i|a| \tan \theta},$$

$$\frac{1}{i}\rho = -L_{i;j}T^i L^j = \pm \frac{a}{a^2}.$$

Solving this system, one gets the following null tetrad:

$$T^i = \{T(\theta), 0, T(\theta), 0\}, \quad -\frac{\partial T(\theta)}{\partial \theta} T(\theta) = \frac{\pm 1}{2|a| \tan \theta};$$

$$N^i = \{N(r, t), N(r, t), 0, 0\},$$

$$\frac{\partial N(r, t)}{\partial t} T(\theta)^2 = -\frac{r}{r^2 + a^2};$$

$$L^i = U^i + iU^i, \quad U^i = \{U(\theta, \phi), 0, 0, U(\theta, \phi)\},$$

$$U(\theta, \phi)^2 = \pm \frac{\phi}{T(\theta)} \frac{|a|}{a^2}.$$

4. Dirac equation. Separating the variables

Taking into account the obtained tetrad (2.5) and Ricci rotation coefficients (2.6), the covariant Dirac equation (3.2) reads

$$\left[i\left(\gamma^0 \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{\Delta}} + \gamma^3 \frac{2a}{\rho} \sqrt{\frac{1 - \cos \theta}{1 + \cos \theta}}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - i\gamma^1 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{r\sqrt{\Delta}}{2\rho^3} + \frac{\Delta'}{4\rho\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) + i\gamma^0 \gamma^2 \gamma^3 \frac{a\sqrt{\Delta}}{2\rho^3} - i\gamma^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{2 \tan \theta}\right) - i\gamma^3 \frac{1}{\rho \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} - M \right] \Psi = 0, \quad (4.1)$$

where we use the notations $\rho^2 = r^2 + a^2$,

$$\Delta = r^2 - r_g r - a^2, \quad \Phi = \frac{\Delta}{\rho^2},$$

$\Psi^T = (\xi, \eta)$, and employ the following basis of γ matrixes

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & I \\ I & 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \gamma^1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_3 \\ \sigma_3 & 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \gamma^2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_1 \\ \sigma_1 & 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

$$\gamma^3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_2 \\ \sigma_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad i\gamma^0\gamma^2\gamma^3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_3 & 0 \end{vmatrix};$$

σ_i designate the Pauli matrices; the bispinor wave function Ψ consists of two spinor components ξ, χ .

From eq. (4.1), we derive equations in 2-spinor form

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma_1 \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \chi_{,2} + \frac{1}{2\rho \tan \theta} \chi \right) + \sigma_2 \left(\frac{1}{\rho \sin \theta} \chi_{,3} - \frac{2a}{\rho} \tan \frac{\theta}{2} \chi_{,0} \right) \\ & + \sigma_3 \left[\frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho} \chi_{,1} + \left(\frac{\Delta'}{4\rho\sqrt{\Delta}} + \frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{2\rho^3} \rho_- \right) \chi \right] + \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \chi_{,0} + iM\xi = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma_1 \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \xi_{,2} + \frac{1}{2\rho \tan \theta} \xi \right) + \sigma_2 \left(\frac{1}{\rho \sin \theta} \xi_{,3} - \frac{2a}{\rho} \tan \frac{\theta}{2} \xi_{,0} \right) \\ & + \sigma_3 \left[\frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho} \xi_{,1} + \left(\frac{\Delta'}{4\sqrt{\Delta}\rho} + \frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{2\rho^3} \rho_+ \right) \xi \right] - \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \xi_{,0} - iM\chi = 0; \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where we use the notations $\partial_\alpha = ,\alpha$, $\rho_+ = r + ia$, $\rho_- = r - ia$. As the NUT-metric is independent on time and ϕ , so we can search two spinors in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= \Delta^{-1/4} \rho_+^{-1/2} e^{-i\epsilon t} e^{im\phi} X(r, \theta), \\ \chi &= \Delta^{-1/4} \rho_-^{-1/2} e^{-i\epsilon t} e^{im\phi} Y(r, \theta); \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

the quantum number m represents the third projection of the total angular momentum, correspondingly it takes the values $m = \pm 1/2, \pm 3/2, \pm 5/2, \dots$. Further we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma_1 D_\theta Y + i\sigma_2 H Y + \sigma_3 D_{r-} Y - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} Y \\ & \quad + iM\rho_- X = 0, \\ & \sigma_1 D_\theta X + i\sigma_2 H X + \sigma_3 D_{r+} X + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} X \\ & \quad - iM\rho_+ Y = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} D_{r\pm} &= \sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \pm \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2}, \quad D_\theta = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{2 \tan \theta}, \\ H &= \frac{m}{\sin \theta} + 2a\epsilon \tan \frac{\theta}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

Applying the following designations for spinors and the Pauli matrices

$$X = \begin{vmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \end{vmatrix}, \quad Y = \begin{vmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \end{vmatrix},$$

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix},$$

equations (4.5) give the system

$$\begin{aligned} (D_\theta + H)Y_2 + \left(D_{r-} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)Y_1 + iM\rho_-X_1 &= 0, \\ (D_\theta - H)Y_1 - \left(D_{r-} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)Y_2 + iM\rho_-X_2 &= 0, \\ (D_\theta + H)X_2 + \left(D_{r+} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)X_1 - iM\rho_+Y_1 &= 0, \\ (D_\theta - H)X_1 - \left(D_{r+} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)X_2 - iM\rho_+Y_2 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

We will apply substitutions with the following structure:

$$X_1 = T_1(\theta)R_1(r), \quad X_2 = T_2(\theta)R_2(r),$$

$$Y_1 = T_3(\theta)R_3(r), \quad Y_2 = T_4(\theta)R_4(r),$$

then we get

$$\begin{aligned} R_4(D_\theta + H)T_4 + T_3\left(D_{r-} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_3 \\ + iM\rho_-T_1R_1 &= 0, \\ R_3(D_\theta - H)T_3 - T_4\left(D_{r-} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 \\ + iM\rho_-T_2R_2 &= 0, \\ R_2(D_\theta + H)T_2 + T_1\left(D_{r+} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 \\ - iM\rho_+T_3R_3 &= 0, \\ R_1(D_\theta - H)T_1 - T_2\left(D_{r+} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 \\ - iM\rho_+T_4R_4 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

Let us apply the shortening notations

$$(D_\theta + H) = a_+, \quad (D_\theta - H) = a_-,$$

$$\left(D_{r-} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) = b_-, \quad \left(D_{r-} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) = b_+,$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} R_4 a_+ T_4 + T_3 b_- R_3 + iM \rho_- T_1 R_1 &= 0, \\ R_3 a_- T_3 - T_4 b_+ R_4 + iM \rho_- T_2 R_2 &= 0, \\ R_2 a_+ T_2 + T_1 b_-^* R_1 - iM \rho_+ T_3 R_3 &= 0, \\ R_1 a_- T_1 - T_2 b_+^* R_2 - iM \rho_+ T_4 R_4 &= 0; \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

here symbol "*" designates the complex conjugation.

Firstly, we impose constraints

$$a_+T_4 = c_1T_1, \quad a_-T_1 = c_2T_4$$

$$\implies a_-a_+T_4 = c_1c_2T_4, \quad a_+a_-T_1 = c_1c_2T_1,$$

$$a_-T_3 = c_3T_2, \quad a_+T_2 = c_4T_3$$

$$\implies a_-a_+T_2 = c_3c_4T_2, \quad a_+a_-T_3 = c_3c_4T_3;$$

In this way, we obtain second order equations for separate functions

$$(a_-a_+ - c_1c_2)T_4 = 0, \quad (a_-a_+ - c_3c_4)T_2 = 0.$$

$$(a_+a_- - c_1c_2)T_1 = 0, \quad (a_+a_- - c_3c_4)T_3 = 0.$$

Let us impose the restriction

$$c_1c_2 = c_3c_4, \quad (4.10)$$

then functions T_2, T_4 may differ only by a multiplier, $T_2 = \mu T_4$. Similarly, from equations

$$(a_+a_- - c_1c_2)T_1 = 0, \quad (a_+a_- - c_3c_4)T_3 = 0$$

it follows the restriction $c_1c_2 = c_3c_4$, so we get $T_1 = \mu_1 T_3$. Taking this in mind, let us turn to four first-order constraints

$$a_+T_4 = c_1\mu_1T_3, \quad a_+\mu T_4 = c_4T_3, \quad a_-\mu_1T_3 = c_2T_4,$$

$$a_-T_3 = c_3\mu T_4;$$

whence follow the restrictions

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{c_4}{\mu} = c_1\mu_1, \quad \frac{c_2}{\mu_1} = c_3\mu \implies \\ \mu\mu_1 = \frac{c_4}{c_1} = \frac{c_2}{c_3}, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_1} = \frac{c_1}{c_4}\mu = \frac{c_3}{c_2}\mu. \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

In this way, we get the constraints

$$T_3 = \frac{c_3}{c_2}\mu T_1, \quad T_4 = \frac{1}{\mu}T_2. \quad (4.12)$$

Therefore, we arrive at more simple substitution (with some freedom in parameters):

$$\Psi = \begin{vmatrix} T_1 R_1 \\ T_2 R_2 \\ \frac{c_3}{c_2} \mu T_1 R_3 \\ \frac{1}{\mu} T_2 R_4 \end{vmatrix}. \quad (4.13)$$

Applying the substitution (4.13) to system (4.7), we get the system with respect to the variables $R_i(r)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(D_{r-} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\mu R_3 + iM\rho - \frac{c_2}{c_3}R_1 + c_4R_4 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r-} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 - iM\rho - \mu R_2 - c_3\mu R_3 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r+} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\frac{c_2}{c_3}R_1 - iM\rho + \mu R_3 + c_4\mu R_2 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r+} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\mu R_2 + iM\rho + R_4 - c_3\frac{c_2}{c_3}R_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

It is convenient to transform the system to the new variables:

$$\tilde{R}_1 = \frac{c_2}{c_3}R_1, \quad \tilde{R}_3 = \mu R_3, \quad \tilde{R}_2 = \mu R_2, \quad \tilde{T}_1 = \frac{1}{\mu_1}T_1. \quad (4.15)$$

Then the substitution (4.13) and system (4.14) take the form:

$$\Psi = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{c_3}{c_2} T_1 \tilde{R}_1 \\ \frac{1}{\mu} T_2 \tilde{R}_2 \\ \frac{c_3}{c_2} T_1 \tilde{R}_3 \\ \frac{1}{\mu} T_2 \tilde{R}_4 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{\mu\mu_1} T_1 \tilde{R}_1 \\ \frac{1}{\mu} T_2 \tilde{R}_2 \\ \frac{1}{\mu\mu_1} T_1 \tilde{R}_3 \\ \frac{1}{\mu} T_2 \tilde{R}_4 \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1}{\mu} \begin{vmatrix} \tilde{T}_1 \tilde{R}_1 \\ T_2 \tilde{R}_2 \\ \tilde{T}_1 \tilde{R}_3 \\ T_2 \tilde{R}_4 \end{vmatrix} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(D_{r-} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\tilde{R}_3 + iM\rho - \tilde{R}_1 + c_4R_4 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r-} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 - iM\rho - \tilde{R}_2 - c_3\tilde{R}_3 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r+} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\tilde{R}_1 - iM\rho + \tilde{R}_3 + c_4\tilde{R}_2 &= 0, \\ \left(D_{r+} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)\tilde{R}_2 + iM\rho + R_4 - c_3\tilde{R}_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

In the following, for shortness, the tilde symbols will be omitted. Taking into account the expressions for operators $D_{r\pm}$ (4.6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_3 + iM(r-ia)R_1 &= -c_4R_4, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 + iM(r+ia)R_4 &= c_3R_1, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 - iM(r+ia)R_3 &= -c_4R_2, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 - iM(r-ia)R_2 &= c_3R_3; \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

recall the angular equations (remembering that here T_1 designates \tilde{T}_1)

$$(D_\theta + H)T_2 = c_4T_1, \quad (D_\theta - H)T_1 = c_3T_2. \quad (4.19)$$

Instead of two parameter c_4 and c_3 , one can preserve only one:

$$\left[(D_\theta + H)(D_\theta - H) - c_3c_4\right]T_1 = 0, \quad -c_3c_4 = \Lambda^2;$$

$$\left[(D_\theta - H)(D_\theta + H) - c_3c_4\right]T_2 = 0, \quad -c_3c_4 = \Lambda^2.$$

Indeed, let $T_1 = a\bar{T}_1$, $T_2 = b\bar{T}_2$, then equations (4.19) read

$$(D_\theta + H)b\bar{T}_2 = c_4a\bar{T}_1, \quad (D_\theta - H)a\bar{T}_1 = c_3b\bar{T}_2.$$

With the use of new notations

$$c_4\frac{a}{b} = i\Lambda, \quad c_3\frac{b}{a} = i\Lambda \quad \implies \Lambda = \sqrt{-c_4c_3},$$

$$a = -\sqrt{c_3}, \quad b = \sqrt{c_4},$$

we obtain ($\sqrt{-c_3c_4} = \Lambda$)

$$(D_\theta + H)\bar{T}_2 = \Lambda\bar{T}_1, \quad (D_\theta - H)\bar{T}_1 = \Lambda\bar{T}_2; \quad (4.20)$$

for definiteness, one can choose $c_3 = \Lambda$, $c_4 = -\Lambda$.

Finally, the equations (4.18), (4.19) take the form:

$$(D_\theta + H)T_2 = -\Lambda T_1, \quad (D_\theta - H)T_1 = \Lambda T_2; \quad (4.21)$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_3 + iM(r - ia)R_1 = \Lambda R_4,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 + iM(r + ia)R_4 = \Lambda R_1,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 - iM(r + ia)R_3 = \Lambda R_2,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 - iM(r - ia)R_2 = \Lambda R_3. \quad (4.22)$$

Let us remark that according the restriction (4.10) there is equivalent which set of parameters (c_3, c_4 or c_1, c_2) we preserve, the consideration performed in the same way arrives us to two possibilities: 1) $c_1 = \Lambda, c_2 = -\Lambda$; 2) $c_1 = -\Lambda, c_2 = \Lambda$. Then from the formula (4.11) one gets $\mu\mu_1 = \pm 1$. These two different modes may be associated with existence of additional operator of the helicity type. This fact points out on that the wave function substitution (4.13) and the obtained equations (4.21)-(4.22) allow us to obtain the Dirac equation solution without loss of generality.

With notations (4.6) the angular system (4.21) takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dT_1}{d\theta} + \left(\frac{1}{2\tan\theta} - \frac{m}{\sin\theta} - 2a\epsilon \tan\frac{\theta}{2}\right)T_1 - \Lambda T_2 &= 0, \\ \frac{dT_2}{d\theta} + \left(\frac{1}{2\tan\theta} + \frac{m}{\sin\theta} + 2a\epsilon \tan\frac{\theta}{2}\right)T_2 + \Lambda T_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.23)$$

At vanishing NUT parameter $a = 0$, we obtain the case of Schwarzschild spacetime:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_3 + iMrR_1 &= \Lambda R_4, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 + iMrR_4 &= \Lambda R_1, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 - iMrR_3 &= \Lambda R_2, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_4 - iMrR_2 &= \Lambda R_3; \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

here two possibilities exist:

$$I.R_4 = +R_1, \quad R_3 = +R_2$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 - iMrR_2 = \Lambda R_2,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 + iMrR_1 = \Lambda R_1;$$

$$II.R_4 = -R_1, \quad R_3 = -R_2,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_1 + iMrR_2 = \Lambda R_2,$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_2 - iMrR_1 = \Lambda R_1.$$

The similar result for Schwarzschild spacetime follows from equations in [26] for the Kerr–Newman spacetime after performing the limiting procedure to Schwarzschild spacetime.

For non-vanishing NUT parameter, we can see from (4.22) that

$$R_1 = R_3^*, \quad R_2 = R_4^*. \quad (4.25)$$

5. Angular equations

In this section, we will solve the angular equations (4.23) in order to get the quantization rule for the separation parameter Λ . We introduce

new functions $F_i = T_i \sqrt{\sin \theta}$, $i = 1, 2$ and new variable $z = \sin^2 \theta/2$.

The equations (4.23) take the form

$$\begin{aligned} F_1' + \frac{m + 4a\epsilon z}{2z(z - 1)} F_1 - \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{(1 - z)z}} F_2 &= 0, \\ F_2' - \frac{m + 4a\epsilon z}{2z(z - 1)} F_2 + \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{(1 - z)z}} F_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

The corresponding 2nd order equations are

$$F_1'' + \frac{2z - 1}{2z(z - 1)} F_1' - \left[\frac{m(m - 1)}{4z^2(z - 1)^2} + \frac{4a^2\epsilon^2}{(z - 1)^2} + \frac{m(4a\epsilon + 1) + 2a\epsilon}{2z(z - 1)^2} + \frac{\Lambda^2}{z(z - 1)} \right] F_1 = 0, \quad (5.2)$$

$$F_2'' + \frac{2z - 1}{2z(z - 1)} F_2' - \left[\frac{m(m + 1)}{4z^2(z - 1)^2} + \frac{4a^2\epsilon^2}{(z - 1)^2} + \frac{m(4a\epsilon - 1) - 2a\epsilon}{2z(z - 1)^2} + \frac{\Lambda^2}{z(z - 1)} \right] F_2 = 0. \quad (5.3)$$

We apply the following substitutions

$$F_1 = z^A(z - 1)^B G_1, \quad F_2 = z^C(z - 1)^D G_2; \quad (5.4)$$

which lead to the hypergeometric-type equations for G_1, G_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} z(1 - z)G_1'' + \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + 4A) - (1 + 2(A + B))z \right) G_1' \\ - \left((A + B)^2 - 4a^2\epsilon^2 - \Lambda^2 \right) G_1 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} z(1 - z)G_2'' + \left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + 4C) - (1 + 2(C + D))z \right) G_2' \\ - \left((C + D)^2 - 4a^2\epsilon^2 - \Lambda^2 \right) G_2 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.6)$$

So that (K_1 and K_2 are yet non-fixed coefficients)

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= K_1 z^A(z - 1)^B {}_2F_1(a_1, b_1, c_1; z), \\ F_2 &= K_2 z^C(z - 1)^D {}_2F_1(a_2, b_2, c_2; z), \end{aligned} \quad (5.7)$$

$$a_1, b_1 = A + B \pm \sqrt{4a^2\epsilon^2 + \Lambda^2}, \quad c_1 = \frac{1}{2}(1 + 4A);$$

$$a_2, b_2 = C + D \pm \sqrt{4a^2\epsilon^2 + \Lambda^2}, \quad c_2 = \frac{1}{2}(1 + 4C).$$

We search for finite solutions F_1, F_2 . To do it, we have studied the functions near singular points $z = 0, z = 1$. The performed analysis gives the following explicit form of the values A, B, C, D : assuming that if $m > 0, \epsilon > 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{m}{2}, \quad C = \frac{m + 1}{2}, \quad B = \frac{4a\epsilon + m + 1}{2}, \\ D &= \frac{4a\epsilon + m}{2}; \end{aligned}$$

and if $m < 0, \epsilon > 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} A &= -\frac{m - 1}{2}, \quad C = -\frac{m}{2}, \\ B &= -\frac{4a\epsilon + m}{2}, \quad D = -\frac{4a\epsilon + m - 1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, introducing the indexes “+” and “-” for the cases of $m > 0$ and $m < 0$, respectively,

the parameters of hypergeometric functions in the explicit form are

$$\begin{aligned} a_1^\pm &= \frac{1}{2} - \sqrt{4a^2\epsilon^2 + \Lambda^2} \pm (2a\epsilon + m), \\ b_1^\pm &= \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{4a^2\epsilon^2 + \Lambda^2} \pm (2a\epsilon + m), \\ c_1^\pm &= 1 \pm (m - \frac{1}{2}), \quad c_2^\pm = c_1^\pm \pm 1, \\ a_2^\pm &= a_1^\pm, \quad b_2^\pm = b_1^\pm. \end{aligned}$$

The quantization rule is found in usual way by imposing the condition that the power series for the hypergeometric function has to be terminated, namely, b has to be a nonpositive integer:

$$\begin{aligned} b_1^\pm &= \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{4a^2\epsilon^2 + \Lambda^2} \pm (2a\epsilon + m) = -n \\ \Rightarrow \Lambda_\pm^2 &= (n + 1/2 \pm m)(n + 1/2 \pm (m + 4a\epsilon)) \\ &= N(N \pm 4a\epsilon); \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

note that at $m < 0$ the following constraint should

be satisfied $-4a\epsilon - m > 0$, whence it follows $4a\epsilon < -m + n + 1/2 = N$.

Now, substituting the solutions (5.7) into eqs. (5.1), we get the relations for the coefficients K_1 and K_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{m > 0}, \\ K_1 &= -\frac{i(1+2m)}{2\Lambda_+} K_2 = -\frac{i(1+2m)}{2\sqrt{N(N+4a\epsilon)}} K_2; \\ \underline{m < 0}, \\ K_2 &= -\frac{i(1-2m)}{2\Lambda_-} K_1 = -\frac{i(1-2m)}{2\sqrt{N(N-4a\epsilon)}} K_1. \end{aligned}$$

Correspondingly, for initial functions T_1, T_2 we obtain the following presentations

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{m > 0}, \\ T_1 &= \frac{(1+2m)}{4\sqrt{N(N+4a\epsilon)}} z^{\frac{(2m-1)}{4}} (1-z)^{2a\epsilon + \frac{2m+1}{4}} {}_2F_1(1+4a\epsilon+2m+n, -n, m+1/2; z); \\ T_2 &= \frac{1}{2} z^{\frac{2m+1}{4}} (1-z)^{2a\epsilon + \frac{(2m-1)}{4}} {}_2F_1(1+4a\epsilon+2m+n, -n, m+3/2; z). \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{m < 0}, \\ T_1 &= \frac{1}{2} z^{-\frac{2m-1}{4}} (1-z)^{-(2a\epsilon + \frac{(2m+1)}{4})} {}_2F_1(1-4a\epsilon-2m+n, -n, -m+3/2; z); \\ T_2 &= \frac{(1-2m)}{4\sqrt{N(N-4a\epsilon)}} z^{-\frac{(2m+1)}{4}} (1-z)^{-(2a\epsilon + \frac{2m-1}{4})} {}_2F_1(1-4a\epsilon-2m+n, -n, -m+1/2; z). \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

Let us note that the analytical dependence of the angular solutions on the energy through the combination $a\epsilon$ is similar to that for the Maxwell equations in NUT spacetime [10]. The form of the angular components for $m > 0$ is illustrated in Fig. 5.

They demonstrate the evident effects of a non-vanishing NUT-charge. Compared with the case of vanishing NUT-charge, the curves are deformed while the topology of curves remains the same.

FIG. 1. (color online) The dependencies of real parts and absolute values of the functions T_1 (solid lines) and T_2 (dashed lines) on the variable θ . The parameters are of $m = 3/2$; $n = 4$; $a = 0$ (black), $a = 1$ (magenta).

6. Radial equations

6.1. The case of massive particle

We have the known restriction on the component of the metrical tensor $g_{00} > 0$, which leads to the inequality $\Phi > 0$, or $\Delta = r^2 - r_g r - a^2 > 0$. The last leads to the following physically interpretable region for the radial variable

$$\Delta = r^2 - r_g r - a^2 = (r - r_1)(r - r_2),$$

$$r > r_2 = \frac{1}{2}(r_g + \sqrt{r_g^2 + 4a^2}),$$

where r_2 determines the location of the exterior event horizon of the NUT black hole.

It is convenient to introduce the dimensionless quantities, $x = \epsilon r, a \rightarrow \epsilon a, M \rightarrow M/\epsilon$. Then the system for radial functions (4.18) transforms to the following one

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_3 + iM(x - ia)R_1 &= \Lambda R_4, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_4 - iM(x - ia)R_2 &= \Lambda R_3, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_1 - iM(x + ia)R_3 &= \Lambda R_2, \\ \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_2 + iM(x + ia)R_4 &= \Lambda R_1. \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

Expressing the functions R_3 and R_1 from the second and fourth equations in (6.1), respectively, and substituting them into the first and third equations, we derive the following system of two second order equations relative to functions R_2 and R_4 :

$$\begin{aligned} R_2'' + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} + \frac{2ia}{a^2 + x^2}\right) R_2' + \left[-\frac{M^2(a^2 + x^2)}{\Delta} + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} + \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta^2} - \frac{a^2}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{2iax}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} - \frac{2ix}{\Delta}\right] R_2 + \frac{iM(x + ia)}{\sqrt{\Delta}(x - ia)} R_4 = 0, \\ R_4'' + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} - \frac{2ia}{a^2 + x^2}\right) R_4' + \left[-\frac{M^2(a^2 + x^2)}{\Delta} + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} - \frac{ia\Delta'}{2\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta^2} - \frac{a^2}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{2iax}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} + \frac{2ix}{\Delta}\right] R_4 - \frac{iM(x - ia)}{\sqrt{\Delta}(x + ia)} R_2 = 0; \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

By the linear combinations of the equations (6.1) in the same way, we get the system for the functions R_3, R_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} R_1'' + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} + \frac{2ia}{a^2 + x^2} \right) R_1' + \left[-\frac{M^2(a^2 + x^2)}{\Delta} + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta^2} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{a^2}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{2iax}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} + \frac{2ix}{\Delta} \right] R_1 - \frac{iM(x + ia)}{\sqrt{\Delta}(x - ia)} R_3 = 0, \\ R_3'' + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} - \frac{2ia}{a^2 + x^2} \right) R_3' + \left[-\frac{M^2(a^2 + x^2)}{\Delta} + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} - \frac{ia\Delta'}{2\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} + \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta^2} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{a^2}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{2iax}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} - \frac{2ix}{\Delta} \right] R_3 + \frac{iM(x - ia)}{\sqrt{\Delta}(x + ia)} R_1 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

Taking into account the symmetry (4.25), it is enough to consider the subsystem for variables R_1, R_3 . In order to simplify the problem, we make substitutions

$$V_3 = \frac{i\sqrt{x + ia}}{\sqrt{x - ia}} (x - x_1)^{-ix_1} (x - x_2)^{-ix_2} \times e^{-ix}. \quad (6.6)$$

$$Z_1 = V_1 R_1, \quad Z_3 = V_3 R_3, \quad (6.4)$$

where

$$V_1 = \frac{\sqrt{x - ia}}{\sqrt{x + ia}} (x - x_1)^{-\frac{1}{2} - ix_1} (x - x_2)^{-\frac{1}{2} - ix_2} \times e^{-i(x - x_1)}, \quad (6.5)$$

These substitutions give the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1'' + \left(\frac{3 + 4ix_1}{2(x - x_1)} + \frac{i(4x_2 - 3i)}{2(x - x_2)} + 2i \right) Z_1' \\ - \frac{(M^2(a^2 + x^2) + \Lambda^2 - 4ix - 1)}{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)} Z_1 - \frac{M}{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)} Z_3 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$Z_3'' + \left(\frac{1 + 4ix_1}{2(x - x_1)} + \frac{i(4x_2 - i)}{2(x - x_2)} + 2i \right) Z_3'$$

Eliminating the variable Z_1 , we derive the fourth order equation for Z_3 :

$$- \frac{(M^2(a^2 + x^2) + \Lambda^2)}{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)} Z_3 - M Z_1 = 0.$$

$$Z_3^{(4)} + 4i \left(1 + \frac{2x_1 - i}{2(x - x_1)} + \frac{2x_2 - i}{2(x - x_2)} \right) Z_3^{(3)} - \left(4 + 2M^2 + \frac{1 + 16x_1^2}{4(x - x_1)^2} + \frac{1 + 16x_2^2}{4(x - x_2)^2} \right) Z_3 = 0.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{4 + 4(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2)) + (3i - 4x_1)^2}{2(x - x_1)(x_1 - x_2)} - \frac{4 + 4(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2)) + (3i - 4x_2)^2}{2(x - x_2)(x_1 - x_2)} \Big) Z_3^{(2)} \\
& - \left(4iM^2 - \frac{1 + 16x_1^2}{4(x - x_1)^3} - \frac{1 + 16x_2^2}{4(x - x_2)^3} + \frac{1 + 16ix_1(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2) - ix_1)}{4(x - x_1)^2(x_1 - x_2)} \right. \\
& - \frac{1 + 16ix_2(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2) - ix_2)}{4(x - x_2)^2(x_1 - x_2)} + \frac{4(1 + 2ix_1)(M^2x_1 - i)}{(x - x_1)(x_1 - x_2)} - \frac{4(1 + 2ix_2)(M^2x_2 - i)}{(x - x_2)(x_1 - x_2)} \Big) Z_3^{(1)} \\
& + \left(M^4 + \frac{i(i + 4x_1)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2))}{2(x - x_1)^3(x_1 - x_2)} - \frac{i(i + 4x_2)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2))}{2(x - x_2)^3(x_1 - x_2)} \right. \\
& + \frac{(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2))(1 - 4ix_1 + 2(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2)))}{2(x - x_1)^2(x_1 - x_2)^2} \\
& + \frac{(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2))(1 - 4ix_2 + 2(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2)))}{2(x - x_2)^2(x_1 - x_2)^2} \\
& - \frac{1}{2(x - x_1)(x_1 - x_2)^3} \left((1 - 4ix_2)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2)) + (1 - 4ix_1)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2)) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4(\Lambda^4 - M^4(a^2 + x_1^2)^2) + 4M^2(1 + 2ix_1)(x_1 - x_2)^2 \right) \\
& + \frac{1}{2(x - x_2)(x_1 - x_2)^3} \left((1 - 4ix_2)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_1^2)) + (1 - 4ix_1)(\Lambda^2 + M^2(a^2 + x_2^2)) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4(\Lambda^4 - M^4(a^2 + x_2^2)^2) + 4M^2(1 + 2ix_2)(x_1 - x_2)^2 \right) \Big) Z_3 = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

In order to study the radiation emitted by the black hole, let us find the approximate equation for the radial function near the exterior horizon $x \rightarrow x_2$. Preserving only the largest terms in the

previous equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_3^{(4)} + \frac{2i(2x_2 - i)}{x - x_2} Z_3^{(3)} - \frac{(16x_2^2 + 1)}{4(x - x_2)^2} Z_3'' \\
+ \frac{(16x_2^2 + 1)}{4(x - x_2)^3} Z_3' \\
+ \frac{i(4x_2 + i)(M^2(a^2 + x_2^2) + \Lambda^2)}{2(x - x_2)^3(x_2 - x_1)} Z_3 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.7}$$

The possible structure for the solutions is $(x - x_2)^A$. Substituting this into eq. (6.7) and neglecting the last term, we get

$$(-2 + A)A(-3 + 2A + 4ix_2)(-1 + 2A + 4ix_2) = 0;$$

whence it follows $A = 0$, $A = 2$, $A = \frac{1}{2}(1 - 4ix_2)$, $A = \frac{1}{2}(3 - 4ix_2)$. Taking into consideration the form of V_3 and the expressions for multipliers when separating the variables (4.4), we obtain the behavior of radial component near x_2 :

$$\Delta^{-\frac{1}{4}} \rho_-^{-\frac{1}{2}} R_3 \sim (x - x_2)^{ix_2 - \frac{1}{4}}; \text{ or } \sim (x - x_2)^{ix_2 + \frac{7}{4}};$$

$$\text{or } (x - x_2)^{\frac{1}{4} - ix_2}; \text{ or } (x - x_2)^{\frac{5}{4} - ix_2}.$$

The first two solutions correspond to the outgoing waves and the last two solutions determine the ingoing waves. The first solution possess the singularity at $x = x_2$, because of that it is nonphysical one and is rejected from the following consideration. Taking into account the factor $e^{i\epsilon t}$, the wave solutions are (recall that $x = \epsilon r$)

$$\Psi_{in} = e^{-i\epsilon t} (r - r_2)^{-i\epsilon r_2 + \frac{1}{4}}, e^{-i\epsilon t} (r - r_2)^{-i\epsilon r_2 + \frac{5}{4}},$$

$$\Psi_{out}(r > r_2) = e^{-i\epsilon t} (r - r_2)^{+i\epsilon r_2 + \frac{7}{4}},$$

or in ordinary notations

$$\Psi_{in} = e^{-i\omega t} (r - r_2)^\gamma (r - r_2)^{-\frac{i}{2\kappa_+}(\omega - \omega_0)},$$

$$\Psi_{out}(r > r_2) = e^{-i\omega t} (r - r_2)^\gamma (r - r_2)^{\frac{i}{2\kappa_+}(\omega - \omega_0)},$$

where $\omega \equiv \epsilon$, $\kappa_+ = 1/2r_2$, $\omega_0 = 0$, γ is the attenuation coefficient.

The tortoise and Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates are defined by [27, 28]

$$\ln(r - r_2) = \frac{1}{r_2^2 + a^2} \frac{\Delta}{dr} \Big|_{r=r_2} \quad r^* = \frac{1}{r_2(r_2 - r_1)}$$

$$\times \frac{(r - r_1)(r - r_2)}{dr} \Big|_{r=r_2} \quad r^* = \frac{1}{r_2} r^* = 2\kappa_+ r^*,$$

$$v = t + r^*, \quad \Rightarrow \quad t = v - \frac{1}{2\kappa_+} \ln(r - r_2).$$

In new coordinates, the solutions take the form

$$\Psi_{in} = e^{-i\omega v} (r - r_2)^\gamma,$$

$$\Psi_{out}(r > r_2) = e^{-i\omega v} (r - r_2)^\gamma (r - r_2)^{\frac{i}{\kappa_+}\omega}.$$

Ψ_{in} is well-behaved when analytically extended inside the horizon $x < x_2$. $(r - r_2)^\gamma$ is also well-behaved function while $(r - r_2)^{\frac{i}{\kappa_+}\omega}$ has a logarithmic singularity at $x = x_2$. The unique continuation of the function according to the Damour-Ruffini method is rotating $-\pi$ through the lower-half complex r plane. Then, the analytic continuation of a real damped part of the outgoing wave on the horizon surface $r < r_2$ is

$$\Psi_{out}(r < r_2) = e^{-i\omega v} (r - r_2)^\gamma (r_2 - r)^{\frac{i}{\kappa_+}\omega} e^{\frac{\pi}{\kappa_+}\omega}.$$

According to [26–28], a scattering probability

$$\Gamma = \left| \frac{\Psi_{out}(x > x_2)}{\Psi_{out}(x < x_2)} \right|^2 \quad (6.8)$$

is the probability of creating a particle-antiparticle pair just outside the exterior horizon. Substituting the outgoing wave into the formula (6.8), we get

$$\Gamma = e^{-4\pi x_2} = e^{-4\pi \epsilon r_2}. \quad (6.9)$$

The mean number \bar{N}_ϵ of fermions emitted with a given energy (in a fixed mode) is determined by the relation (ignoring the backscattering effect):

$$\bar{N}_\epsilon = \frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma + 1} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{4\pi \epsilon r_2}}. \quad (6.10)$$

We get the Fermi–Dirac distribution

$$\bar{N}_\epsilon = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(\epsilon - \epsilon_0)/T}}, \quad T = \frac{1}{4\pi r_2} = \frac{1}{2\pi(r_g + \sqrt{r_g^2 + 4a^2})}. \quad (6.11)$$

This expression for Hawking temperature coincides with the result obtained for the Taub-NUT black hole in [6]. Since $r_2 > r_g$ at all real

values a , the Hawking temperature decreases with the increase of the NUT charge, this corresponds to decreasing the probability of particle-antiparticle pair production. It should be noted that in contrast to the Kerr–Newman spacetime [26], the obtained scattering probability does

not depend on the third projection of the total angular momentum m .

The asymptotic behavior at infinity for the function Z_3 can be represented as the superposition of ingoing and outgoing damped waves

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta^{-1/4} \rho_-^{-1/2} R_3 \sim c_1 R_{\text{out}} + c_2 R_{\text{in}} \\ & \sim c_1 x^{-\frac{3}{2}+ix_g} \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma^2}{2\sqrt{1-M^2}}\right) \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{12\Gamma^2 + 2\Gamma(8+\Gamma^2-9i\Gamma)x_g + \Gamma^4 x_g^2}{1-M^2}} e^{+i\sqrt{1-M^2}x} \\ & + c_2 x^{-\frac{3}{2}+ix_g} \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma^2}{2\sqrt{1-M^2}}\right) \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{12\Gamma^2 + 2\Gamma(8+\Gamma^2-9i\Gamma)x_g + \Gamma^4 x_g^2}{1-M^2}} e^{-i\sqrt{1-M^2}x}; \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

where $\Gamma = -i(1 \pm \sqrt{1-M^2})$. Let us recall, that here M is renormalized on the energy ϵ ($M \equiv M/\epsilon$). As should be expected, the asymptotic behavior at infinity does not depend on the NUT parameter, but is determined by the mass of the black hole M_{BH} ($x_g = 2M_{BH}$), and the mass and the energy of the particle.

Let us show that there exists specific peculiarity due to the non-vanishing NUT-charge. Indeed, taking into account the identities $R_1 = R_3^*$ and $R_2 = R_4^*$, let us perform the following combination over equations in (6.1):

$$eq.1 \times R_1 + eq.3 \times R_3 - eq.2 \times R_2 - eq.4 \times R_4,$$

then we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{\Delta}(R_1 R_1^* - R_2 R_2^*)' + iM \left[(x - ia)(R_1^2 + R_2^2) \right. \\ & \left. - (x + ia)\left(\left(R_1^*\right)^2 + \left(R_2^*\right)^2\right) \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (6.13)$$

where the derivative over r is denoted by a prime.

For Schwarzschild metric, at $a = 0$, from the system of four equations (6.1) we have the only two independent and conjugate equations, $R_1 = R_2^*$, and correspondingly the second term in eq. (6.13) vanishes identically. Therefore, the absolute values of radial components are equal, $|R_1| = |R_2|$. As one can see from (6.13), NUT

charge results in non-equal amplitudes, $|R_1| \neq |R_2|$, for massive particles (with $M \neq 0$). The situation for massless case seems to be completely different, as $M = 0$ the equation (6.13) takes the form: $(R_1 R_1^* - R_2 R_2^*)' = 0$. The solution of the last gives the amplitude equality $|R_1| = |R_2|$.

6.2. The case of massless particle

In the massless case, the equations (6.1) are simplified: they may be divided into two unlinked subsystems

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_3 = \Lambda R_4, \\ & \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_4 = \Lambda R_3; \end{aligned} \quad (6.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_1 = \Lambda R_2, \\ & \left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) R_2 = \Lambda R_1. \end{aligned} \quad (6.15)$$

The system (6.14) is conjugated to (6.15), by this reason it is enough to consider only the subsystem (6.15). We readily find the 2nd order equations for separate functions

$$\Delta R_1'' + \left[\frac{2ia\Delta}{a^2 + x^2} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta' \right] R_1' + \left[-\Lambda^2 + 2ix + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta} - \frac{a(a + 2ix)\Delta}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta} \right] \times R_1 = 0, \quad (6.16)$$

$$\Delta R_2'' + \left[\frac{2ia\Delta}{a^2 + x^2} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta' \right] R_2' + \left[-\Lambda^2 - 2ix + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta} - \frac{a(a + 2ix)\Delta}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2(a^2 + x^2)} + \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta} \right] \times R_2 = 0. \quad (6.17)$$

Applying the substitution (6.4)–(6.5), from eq. (6.16) we obtain the following equation for Z_1 :

$$Z_1'' + \left(\frac{i(4x_1 - 3i)}{2(x - x_1)} + \frac{i(4x_2 - 3i)}{2(x - x_2)} + 2i \right) Z_1' + \frac{1 + 4ix - \Lambda^2}{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)} Z_1 = 0. \quad (6.18)$$

In the new variable

$$v = \frac{x - x_2}{x_1 - x_2},$$

eq. (6.18) takes the form

$$Z_1'' + \left((z_1 - z_2) + \frac{z_2}{v} + \frac{z_1}{v - 1} \right) Z_1' + \frac{-2 - \Lambda^2 + 2z_2 + 2(z_1 - z_2)v}{v(v - 1)} Z_1 = 0, \quad (6.19)$$

where $z_1 = 2ix_1 + 3/2$, $z_2 = 2ix_2 + 3/2$. Its general solution can be expressed in terms of the confluent

Heun functions:

$$Z_1 = C_{11} \text{HeunC} \left[q_{11}; \alpha_{11}, \gamma_{11}, \delta_1, \varepsilon; v \right] + C_{12} v^{1-\gamma_{11}} \text{HeunC} \left[q_{12}; \alpha_{12}, \gamma_{12}, \delta_1, \varepsilon; v \right],$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} q_{11} &= 2 + \Lambda^2 - 2z_2, & \alpha_{11} &= 2(z_1 - z_2), \\ \varepsilon &= (z_1 - z_2), & \gamma_{11} &= z_2, & \delta_1 &= z_1; \\ q_{12} &= (-\delta_1 + \varepsilon)(1 - \gamma_{11})q_{11}, \\ \alpha_{12} &= \alpha_{11} + \varepsilon(1 - \gamma_{11}), & \gamma_{12} &= 2 - \gamma_{11}. \end{aligned}$$

Let us turn back to the original variable R_1 as

$$R_1 \sim e^{i\varepsilon(r-r_1)} (r - r_1)^{\frac{1}{2} + i\varepsilon r_1} (r - r_2)^{\frac{1}{2} + i\varepsilon r_2} \frac{\sqrt{r + ia}}{\sqrt{r - ia}} \left(C_{11} \text{HeunC} \left(q_{11}; \alpha_{11}, \gamma_{11}, \delta_1, \varepsilon; \frac{r - r_2}{r_1 - r_2} \right) + C_{12} v^{1-\gamma_{11}} \text{HeunC} \left(q_{12}; \alpha_{12}, \gamma_{12}, \delta_1, \varepsilon; \frac{r - r_2}{r_1 - r_2} \right) \right). \quad (6.20)$$

In turn, with the use of substitution $Z_2 = V_2 R_2$, where

$$V_2 = \frac{e^{-i(x-x_1)} \sqrt{a+ix} (-x+x_1)^{-ix_1} (-x+x_2)^{-ix_2}}{\sqrt{a-ix}}$$

for the function R_2 related to eq. (6.17) we derive that

$$R_2 \sim e^{i\epsilon(r-r_1)} (r-r_1)^{i\epsilon r_1} (r-r_2)^{i\epsilon r_2} \frac{\sqrt{r+ia}}{\sqrt{r-ia}} \times \left(C_{21} \text{HeunC}(q_{21}; \alpha_{21}, \gamma_{21}, \delta_2, \epsilon; \frac{r-r_2}{r_1-r_2}) + C_{22} v^{1-\gamma_{21}} \text{HeunC}(q_{22}; \alpha_{22}, \gamma_{22}, \delta_2, \epsilon; \frac{r-r_2}{r_1-r_2}) \right); \tag{6.21}$$

$$q_{21} = -\Lambda^2, \quad \alpha_{21} = 0, \quad \gamma_{21} = z_2 - 1, \quad \delta_2 = z_1 - 1; \\ q_{22} = (-\delta_2 + \epsilon)(1 - \gamma_{21})q_{21}, \\ \alpha_{22} = \alpha_{21} + \epsilon(1 - \gamma_{21}), \quad \gamma_{22} = 2 - \gamma_{21}.$$

Taking into account the multipliers evolved at separation procedure, the complete radial function (for example, for the component R_1) can be presented as follows

$$\Delta^{-1/4} \rho_+^{-1/2} R_1 = C_{11} R_{11} + C_{12} R_{12}. \tag{6.22}$$

The behavior of the this functions R_{11} and R_{12} is illustrated in Fig. 2

Series expansion of the confluent Heun function

$$Z(v) = \text{HeunC} \left[q; \alpha, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon; v \right] = v(v-1) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n v^n$$

around the regular singular point $v = 0$ ($x = x_2$) gives the three-term recurrence relation

$$C_{n+1} c_{n-1} + B_{n+1} c_n - A_{n+1} c_{n+1} = 0, \\ A_{n+1} = (n+1)(\gamma+n), \\ B_{n+1} = (n(\gamma+\delta+n-\epsilon-1)-q), \\ C_{n+1} = (\alpha+(n-1)\epsilon); \quad n \geq 2.$$

Let us restrict ourselves to the transcendental confluent Heun functions, which are obtained by imposing the δ_N -condition [29, 30]: $C_{n+2} = 0$, whence it follows $\alpha + n\epsilon = 0$. Only the components with C_{12} and C_{22} in general solutions

FIG. 2. (color online) The real (solid lines) and imaginary (dashed lines) parts of the functions R_{11} , R_{12} of the wave function (6.22) for the case of massless fermion. The parameters are of $r_g = 1$; $\epsilon = 1$; $N = 3$; $a = 0$ (black), $a = 0.1$ (red).

(6.20), (6.21) satisfy this constrain, at this we obtain energies as

$$\epsilon_I = -i \frac{3+2n}{4r_2} = -i \frac{3+2n}{2(r_g + \sqrt{r_g^2 + 4a^2})}.$$

The derived energy quasispectrum determines the frequencies which represent the scattering resonances of the fields in the black hole spacetime [26, 31]. The resonances characterize the poles of the transmission (reflection) amplitudes dependencies on the energy. In opposite to the case of Kerr black hole [26], the values of resonant energies do not possess the real part and are imaginary ones, similarly to the Schwarzschild case. It seems to be related with absence of the bound states. Nevertheless, the non-vanishing NUT charge influences the wave characteristics. Thus, the resonant energies associated with the massless fermion are decreased with the rise of NUT charge a compared with the Schwarzschild black hole levels.

6.2.1. Effective potential

Let us discuss the possibility of describing the system under consideration using the concept of the effective potential. To this end, we introduce the new variables $f(x) = R_1 + R_2$, $g(x) = i(R_1 - R_2)$. Then the radial equations (6.15) take the form

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{\Delta}f' + \left(\frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{a^2 + x^2} - \Lambda\right)f + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)}{\sqrt{\Delta}}g &= 0, \\ \sqrt{\Delta}g' + \left(\frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{a^2 + x^2} + \Lambda\right)g - \frac{(a^2 + x^2)}{\sqrt{\Delta}}f &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

The corresponding second order equations are as

$$\begin{aligned}f'' + \left(\frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} - \frac{2}{x + ia}\right)f' + \left(\frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} + \frac{2\Lambda x}{\sqrt{\Delta}(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{a(a + 4ix)}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda\Delta'}{2\Delta^{3/2}} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta}\right)f \\ = 0,\end{aligned}\tag{6.23}$$

$$\begin{aligned}g'' + \left(\frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} - \frac{2}{x + ia}\right)g' + \left(\frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{\Delta(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{2\Lambda x}{\sqrt{\Delta}(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{a(a + 4ix)}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{\Lambda\Delta'}{2\Delta^{3/2}} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta}\right)g \\ = 0.\end{aligned}\tag{6.24}$$

Let us find a special variable w , which generalizes tortoise-like coordinate and transforms the equations (6.23)–(6.24) to the structure

$$\left[\frac{d^2}{dw^2} + P(w)\right]f = 0, \quad \left[\frac{d^2}{dw^2} + Q(w)\right]g = 0,\tag{6.25}$$

where $P(w)$ and $Q(w)$ may be considered as effective squared linear momentums, shortly – potentials. The variable w is determined by the equation

$$\frac{d^2w}{dx^2} + \left[\frac{\Delta'}{\Delta} - \frac{2}{x + ia}\right]\frac{dw}{dx} = 0,\tag{6.26}$$

whence we readily find that

$$\begin{aligned}w = x \\ + \frac{(a - ix_1)^2 \ln(x - x_1) - (a - ix_2)^2 \ln(x - x_2)}{x_2 - x_1}, \\ x > x_2 > x_1.\end{aligned}$$

In the limiting case of the Schwarzschild metric ($a = 0$) with horizon $x_g = 1$, one gets $w = x + \ln(x - 1)$ which is ordinary tortoise coordinate, in this case eqs. (6.23)–(6.24) coincides with the equations obtained in [32]. The potentials P and Q are

$$\begin{aligned}
P &= \frac{(x-x_1)^2(x-x_2)^2}{(a-ix)^4} \left(\frac{(a^2+x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{\Delta(a^2+x^2)} + \frac{2\Lambda x}{\sqrt{\Delta}(a^2+x^2)} - \frac{a(a+4ix)}{(a^2+x^2)^2} - \frac{\Lambda\Delta'}{2\Delta^{3/2}} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} \right), \\
Q &= \frac{(x-x_1)^2(x-x_2)^2}{(a-ix)^4} \left(\frac{(a^2+x^2)^2}{\Delta^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{\Delta(a^2+x^2)} - \frac{2\Lambda x}{\sqrt{\Delta}(a^2+x^2)} - \frac{a(a+4ix)}{(a^2+x^2)^2} + \frac{\Lambda\Delta'}{2\Delta^{3/2}} - \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Delta} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{6.27}$$

The potential $P(x)$ is illustrated in Fig. 3. As one can see from Fig. 3(a)–(b), when the NUT-charge increases, the real and imaginary parts change the character of their behavior to the opposite. The dependence of the absolute value of the effective potentials $P(x)$ and $Q(x)$ is presented by the monotonically decreasing curve, similarly to the case of the Schwarzschild metric, which evidences the absence of the bound states for such systems. However, it should be specially noted that the potentials are complex-valued functions, while at imaginary values of NUT-charge $a = i|a|$ they become real-valued. At the exterior horizon $x \rightarrow x_2$ they behave as

$$\begin{aligned}
P = Q &= \frac{(x_2 - ia)^2}{(x_2 + ia)^2} = \frac{(a^2 - x_2^2)^2 - 4a^2x_2^2}{(a^2 + x_2^2)^2} \\
&\quad + i \frac{4ax_2(a^2 - x_2^2)}{(a^2 + x_2^2)^2}
\end{aligned}$$

and at infinity $x \rightarrow \infty$, the potentials tend to the unit, $P = Q = 1$.

7. Black hole with a small NUT parameter

In the limiting case of the Schwarzschild black hole, the radial components of the wave function obey the conditions

$$R_4 = -R_1, \quad R_3 = -R_2, \tag{7.1}$$

as one can see from eq. (6.1). Let us assume small value of the NUT-charge, $a \ll 1$, so that the radial functions R_4 and R_3 are only slightly differ from the conditions (7.1):

$$R_4 = -R_1 + af_{14}, \quad R_3 = -R_2 + af_{23}.$$

Taking this in mind, from eqs. (6.1) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) (R_2 - af_{23}) \\
&\quad - (iMx + Ma + \Lambda)R_1 = -a\Lambda f_{14}, \\
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) (R_1 - af_{14}) \\
&\quad + (iMx + Ma + \Lambda)R_2 = -a\Lambda f_{23}, \\
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) R_1 \\
&\quad + (iMx - Ma - \Lambda)R_2 = a(iMx - Ma)f_{23}, \\
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) R_2 \\
&\quad - (iMx - Ma + \Lambda)R_1 = -a(iMx - Ma)f_{14}.
\end{aligned} \tag{7.2}$$

Removing the right-hand parts in last two equations at small a , we arrive at two equations with respect to R_1, R_2

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) R_1 \\
&\quad + (iMx - Ma - \Lambda)R_2 = 0, \\
&\left(\sqrt{\Delta} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}} \right) R_2 \\
&\quad - (iMx - Ma + \Lambda)R_1 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{7.3}$$

The equations (7.3) lead to the 2nd order equations

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta R_1'' + \left[\frac{2ia\Delta}{a^2 + x^2} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta' + \frac{iM\Delta}{\Lambda - iM(x + ia)} \right] R_1' \\ & + \left[-\Lambda^2 + 2ix + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta} - \frac{a(a + 2ix)\Delta}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2(a^2 + x^2)} - \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta} \right. \\ & \left. - M^2(x + ia)^2 - \frac{M(x^2 + a^2)}{\Lambda - iM(x + ia)} - \frac{aM\Delta}{(\Lambda - iM(x + ia))(a^2 + x^2)} \right] R_1 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta R_2'' + \left[\frac{2ia\Delta}{a^2 + x^2} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta' - \frac{iM\Delta}{\Lambda + iM(x + ia)} \right] R_2' \\ & + \left[-\Lambda^2 - 2ix + \frac{(a^2 + x^2)^2}{\Delta} - \frac{a(a + 2ix)\Delta}{(a^2 + x^2)^2} + \frac{ia\Delta'}{2(a^2 + x^2)} + \frac{i(a^2 + x^2)\Delta'}{2\Delta} \right. \\ & \left. - M^2(x + ia)^2 - \frac{M(x^2 + a^2)}{\Lambda + iM(x + ia)} + \frac{aM\Delta}{(\Lambda + iM(x + ia))(a^2 + x^2)} \right] R_2 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7.5)$$

For brevity, we will follow only results for R_1 . Applying in eq. (7.4) the substitution $Z_1 = V_{1a}R_1$ with

$$V_{1a} = i \frac{e^{ix_1} \sqrt{a + ix} (x - x_1)^{-1/2 - ix_1} (x - x_2)^{-1/2 - ix_2}}{\sqrt{a - ix}},$$

we obtain the following equation for Z_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} & Z_1'' + \left(\frac{i(4x_1 - 3i)}{2(x - x_1)} + \frac{i(4x_2 - 3i)}{2(x - x_2)} - \frac{M}{i\Lambda + Mx + iaM} \right) Z_1' \\ & + \left(1 - M^2 + \frac{A + Bx + Cx^2}{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)(i\Lambda + Mx + iaM)} \right) Z_1 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7.6)$$

where

$$C = 2M (M^2(2ia + x_g) - 2x_g).$$

$$A = -i\Lambda (8a^2 - 2\Lambda^2 + 3ix_g + 2) - 2iaM (a(4a - 3)$$

$$-\Lambda^2 + 1) + (3a - 1)Mx_g,$$

In the variable $v = (x - x_2)/(x_1 - x_2)$, we obtain the simpler description

$$B = -M (16a^2 + (2aM^2 - 4a - 1) (2a - ix_g))$$

$$Z_1'' + \left(\frac{z_2}{v} + \frac{z_1}{v - 1} + \frac{-1}{v - c} \right) Z_1'$$

$$-i\Lambda (-2M^2(x_g + 2ia) + 4x_g + 2i) + 2\Lambda^2 M,$$

$$+ \left(1 - M^2 + \frac{(A + Bx_2 + Cx_2^2)/(z_1 - z_2) + (B + 2Cx_2)v + C(z_1 - z_2)v^2}{Mv(v - 1)(v - c)} \right) Z_1 = 0,$$

$$c = \frac{i\Lambda + Mx_2 + iaM}{M(z_2 - z_1)}.$$

The last equation reduces significantly if $M = 1$ and $C = 0$. These conditions give the

following constraint on the parameters

$$2M(M^2(2ia + x_g) - 2x_g) = 0, \text{ or} \\ x_g = \frac{2iaM^2}{2 - M^2}, \quad M = 1. \quad (7.7)$$

8. Extremal NUT black hole

Let us consider a special case when $M = 1$, then from the condition (7.7) we get $x_g = 2ia$. Let us examine imaginary values of a , related to an extremal NUT metric with the imaginary NUT charge. In this case, $x_1 = x_2 = x_g/2$ which bounds the region of positive values of the expression under the square root, $(x_g^2 + 4a^2)$.

The Kerr black hole with a single (degenerated) horizon was referred as an extremal Kerr black hole [33]. By this reason we will use the term "extremal NUT black hole".

Due to equality $z_1 = z_2$ and condition (7.7), eq. (7.6) takes the form

$$Z_1'' + \left(\frac{3 - 4a}{(x - ia)} - \frac{1}{x - c_e} \right) Z_1' \\ + \frac{b_e(-i - c_e + x)}{(x - ia)^2(x - c_e)} Z_1 = 0, \quad (8.1)$$

where $c_e = -i(a + \Lambda)$, $b_e = (2a - \Lambda - 1)(2a + \Lambda)$. In new variable $v_e = \frac{x - ia}{c_e - ia}$, we get

$$Z_1'' + \left(\frac{3 - 4a}{v_e} - \frac{1}{v_e - 1} \right) Z_1' + \frac{b_e(s_e + v_e)}{v_e^2(v_e - 1)} Z_1 = 0, \\ s_e = \frac{1}{a + ic_e} - 1. \quad (8.2)$$

Thus, we have an equation of the hypergeometric type, its general solution reads

$$Z_1 = c_1 v_e^{2a - \alpha_e - 1} {}_2F_1 \left[-\alpha_e - \frac{\beta_e}{2} - \frac{1}{2}, -\alpha_e + \frac{\beta_e}{2} - \frac{1}{2}; 1 - 2\alpha_e; v_e \right] \\ + c_2 v_e^{2a + \alpha_e - 1} {}_2F_1 \left[\alpha_e - \frac{\beta_e}{2} - \frac{1}{2}, \alpha_e + \frac{\beta_e}{2} - \frac{1}{2}; 1 + 2\alpha_e; v_e \right], \quad (8.3)$$

Taking into account the following definitions:

$$\alpha_e = \sqrt{(1 - 2a)^2 + b_e s_e} = \Lambda,$$

$$\beta_e = \sqrt{(1 - 4a)^2 - 4b_e} = (1 + 2\Lambda),$$

the solution (8.3) simplifies

$$Z_1 = c_1 v^{2a - \Lambda - 1} + c_2 v^{2a + \Lambda - 1} \left(1 - \frac{2\Lambda v}{2\Lambda + 1} \right). \quad (8.4)$$

Correspondingly, the complete radial function takes the form

$$\Delta^{-\frac{1}{4}} \rho_+^{-\frac{1}{2}} V_{1a}^{-1} Z_1 \\ = C_1 R_{11} + C_2 R_{12} = C_1 (x - |a|)^{-1 - \Lambda} \\ + C_2 (x - |a|)^{-1 + \Lambda} \left(1 + \frac{2\Lambda(x - |a|)}{(1 + 2\Lambda)(i\Lambda + 2|a|)} \right), \quad (8.5)$$

where $a = -i|a|$, and according to formula (5.8) the separation constant equals $\Lambda = \pm \sqrt{N(N - 4i|a|\epsilon)}$. The behavior of the terms $F_{11} = (x - |a|)^2 R_{11}$ and $F_{12} = C_2(x - |a|)R_{12}$ is presented in Fig. 4 (the multipliers attenuate the strong damping and are introduced for better visualization of functions behavior). As one can see, the increasing of NUT charge $|a|$ leads to the significant decrease of the R_{11} and R_{12} amplitudes.

At small values of the energy ϵ , we can perform the approximation $\Lambda = \pm \sqrt{N(N - 4i|a|\epsilon)} \approx \pm N(1 - 2i|a|\epsilon/N)$.

FIG. 3. (color online) The real (up) and imaginary (down) parts of the potential P in dependence on radial coordinate x at different values of the NUT parameter a , $a = 1$ (solid black line), 0.9 (dashed dark-grey line), 0.7 (dashed grey line), 0.5 (dashed light-grey line), 0.3 (dashed brown line), 0.1 (dotted brown line), 0 (dotted magenta line).

Then the real part of R_{11} can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Re}[R_{11}] &= \operatorname{Re}\left[(x - |a|)^{-1-\Lambda}\right] \approx (x - |a|)^{-1\mp N} \\ &\quad \times \operatorname{Re}\left[e^{\pm 2i|a|\epsilon \ln(x-|a|)}\right] \\ &= \pm (x - |a|)^{-1\mp N} \cos\left(2|a|\epsilon \ln(x - |a|)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (8.6)$$

The expansion of the logarithm near any

FIG. 4. (color online) The real (solid lines) and imaginary (dashed lines) parts of the components F_{11} , F_{12} of the wave function (8.5) at the NUT parameter $a = 0.05$ (black) and $a = 0.1$ (red); $N = 1$, $\epsilon = 10$.

fixed point x_0 has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(x - |a|) &= \ln\left((x_0 - |a|) + (x - x_0)\right) \\ &\approx \frac{1}{x_0 - |a|}x + \left(\ln(x_0 - |a|) - \frac{x_0}{x_0 - |a|}\right) \\ &\equiv k_{x_0}x + \varphi_{x_0}. \end{aligned}$$

In other words, in the small vicinity of the point x_0 ($x \ll 2x_0 - |a|$) the formula (8.6) is rewritten as

$$\operatorname{Re}[R_{11}] = \pm (x - |a|)^{-1\mp N} \cos\left(2|a|\epsilon(k_{x_0}x + \varphi_{x_0})\right).$$

So, one can conclude that the wave number k_{x_0} increases with the rise of the NUT charge $|a|$; the phase shift φ_{x_0} also changes for non-zero NUT charge in comparison with the Schwarzschild case. These effects are revealed in Fig. 4. These peculiarities may be used to distinguish between Schwarzschild and NUT black holes.

9. Discussion

Instead of widely used the Newman–Penrose formalism [23], we have applied the usual tetrad Weyl–Fock–Ivanenko method [19–22, 34] to handle with the Dirac equation in NUT space.

It should be noted that radial systems for original NUT and Taub-NUT spaces are the same. In [11], the Dirac equation in the background of Taub-NUT space has been considered and the separation of the variables has been performed by applying the following substitution:

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= R_{+\frac{1}{2}}(r)T_1(\theta), & X_2 &= R_{-\frac{1}{2}}(r)T_2(\theta), \\ Y_1 &= R_{-\frac{1}{2}}(r)T_1(\theta), & Y_2 &= R_{+\frac{1}{2}}(r)T_2(\theta), \end{aligned} \quad (9.1)$$

which previously successfully used for separating the variables in the Dirac equation in the background of Kerr and Kerr–Newman spacetimes [26, 35]. However, being applied to Dirac problem in NUT space, this substitution gives the inconsistent system of four equations. Indeed, applying the substitution (9.1) to the equations (4.5), one get

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad + iM(r - ia)R_{+\frac{1}{2}} = \Lambda R_{+\frac{1}{2}}, \\ &\left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} - \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad + iM(r + ia)R_{+\frac{1}{2}} = \Lambda R_{+\frac{1}{2}}, \\ &\left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_{+\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad - iM(r + ia)R_{-\frac{1}{2}} = \Lambda R_{-\frac{1}{2}}, \\ &\left(\sqrt{\Delta}\frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2} + \frac{i\epsilon\rho^2}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right)R_{+\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad - iM(r - ia)R_{-\frac{1}{2}} = \Lambda R_{-\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9.2)$$

Subtracting the first equation from the second, and also the fourth equation from the third, one obtain algebraic relations

$$\frac{2ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2}R_{-\frac{1}{2}} - 2MaR_{+\frac{1}{2}} = 0,$$

$$\frac{2ia\sqrt{\Delta}}{\rho^2}R_{+\frac{1}{2}} + 2MaR_{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0,$$

the last system leads to

$$\left(\frac{\Delta}{\rho^4} - M^2\right)R_{+\frac{1}{2}} = 0, \quad \left(\frac{\Delta}{\rho^4} - M^2\right)R_{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0.$$

Because $\left(\frac{\Delta}{\rho^4} - M^2\right) \neq 0$ for any radial coordinate r , we conclude that the unique solution for the system (9.2) is trivial, $R_{+\frac{1}{2}} = R_{-\frac{1}{2}} \equiv 0$.

We have proved that for the quantum-mechanical problem of a massive particle in the NUT spacetime (4.22) it is impossible to rearrange the four radial equations by applying the linear constraints for radial functions, to reduce the problem to two first order differential equations. It should be noted, that the choice of the spinors (4.4) in some different form would allow to simplify the problem of four radial equations to two ones. It will be task of our future investigations. In this work, we have analyzed the system of four linked differential equations (4.22) and have solved it for massless particle. Recently [36], solutions of the Dirac equation for a massless particle have been described within the Frobenius approach. In the present paper, we have constructed the solution in terms of the confluent Heun functions. In contrast to the Frobenius-type solutions, the Heun confluent functions allow to get the scattering resonance frequencies [31]. We have shown that the presence of NUT charge leads to the decreasing resonance energies compared with the Schwarzschild black hole.

For the NUT metric, the Riemann curvature tensor turns to zero at infinity, but the presence of the Misner string makes the NUT spacetime asymptotically non-flat and anisotropic [5]. Though the NUT metric possesses the string singularity and, correspondingly, there exist closed timelike curves, in [37] it was shown that the geodesics of the freely falling observers are not closed timelike curves. So, NUT metric avoids causality violation, and it can be considered as physically meaningful. By this reason, the primordial black hole with NUT charge seems to be an intriguing object in early Universe models

[38]. As shown in [38], the low-energy (related to the ordinary mass less than 5×10^{11} kg) primordial black hole with NUT charge have the smaller Hawking temperature and may not be decayed due to the Hawking radiation by now.

In [6, 38], the Hawking radiation was defined in the conventional way, in contrast to this, in the present paper we have found the Hawking temperature from the structure of the Dirac equation solutions, and have demonstrated the decreasing of the probability of particle-antiparticle production on the event horizon. This supports the result of [38], that the primordial black holes with large NUT charge, could be preserved in the present Universe. As known, the Hawking radiation even from the Schwarzschild black hole was not observed till now. But if such experiments will exist in future, they may serve an experimental test for distinguishing black holes of different types. Let compare the Hawking radiation for the NUT and Kerr black holes, the last is much more examined. As it was shown in [26], the Hawking temperature for the Kerr black hole is determined by the formula (with the notations used in our paper $r_g = 2M_{BH}$, M_{BH} is a mass of black hole):

$$T_{\text{Kerr}} = \frac{\sqrt{r_g^2 - 4J^2}}{2\pi r_g (r_g + \sqrt{r_g^2 - 4J^2})},$$

here J is the angular momentum per unit mass. For NUT black hole, we correspondingly have

$$T_{\text{NUT}} = \frac{1}{2\pi (r_g + \sqrt{r_g^2 + 4a^2})}.$$

As one can see in Fig. 5 the rotation of black hole as well as NUT charge result in decrease of the Hawking temperature, but the characters of these effects are different.

We have noted that the imaginary NUT parameter a leads to complex-valued metric (2.1). As known in quantum gravity models, the complex-valued metrics may be able to regularise the big bang by using a non-singular geometry. However, not all complex metrics may be considered as physically interpretable, the

FIG. 5. The Hawking temperature for Kerr (up) and NUT (down) black holes in dependence on the angular momentum J and NUT-parameter a , respectively.

relevant criteria of applicability are described in [39, 40].

Recall that in quantum mechanics the use of the complex wave functions is admissible when the observables quantities are real. Interestingly, that the effective potential for massless particle is complex-valued for real NUT parameter. However, at imaginary NUT charge the effective potential is real-valued (Section 6.2.1).

In [41], it was shown that re-scaling of the vacuum Weyl metrics and transforming it to a complex parameter yields axially symmetric vacuum solutions with wormhole topology; their sources can be viewed as thin rings of the negative tension encircling the throats. Such ring wormholes do not show infinite red or blue shifts as well as pathologies like closed timelike curves. The supercritically charged black holes with NUT parameter belong to these traversable wormholes [37]. For pure (uncharged) black hole with a real NUT parameter, the wormhole solutions do

not exist. However, when using imaginary NUT parameter values one can obtain a wormhole solution.

According [42], the entropy of an extremal black hole should vanish, though its event horizon can have nonzero area. For instance, the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy formula $S = A/4$ cannot be applied to the extremal case for Kerr and Reissner–Nordström solutions. Because of that, transition to extremality for these spacetime models is not continuous [43]. For extremal NUT black hole (Section 8), we face the opposite situation. The entropy of the NUT black hole equals $S = \pi(a^2 + r_2^2)$ [6], so it vanishes $S = 0$ if $r_2 = ia$. This fact makes this complex-valued metric to be interesting for theoretical investigation.

10. Conclusion

So, the Dirac equation for the particle in the background of the Newman–Unti–Tamburino spacetime has been derived by applying the tetrad formalism. The separation procedure has been performed and the general wave function substitution (4.13) has been found. The obtained two different modes point out on the existence of additional operator of the helicity type. The finding of the explicit form of this operator is a task of the future investigations.

The system of two differential equations for angular functions and the system of four differential equations for radial functions have been derived. The angular equations have been solved in terms of hypergeometric functions and the NUT-charge dependent quantization rule for the angular separation constant have been found. The radial system has been solved for special cases of the massless particle and for massive particle with a fixed energy near extremal NUT

black hole. For the massless fermion, we have been constructed the solution of the radial system of Dirac equation in terms of the confluent Heun functions. We have demonstrated that, in opposite to the case of Kerr black hole, the values of resonant energies do not possess the real part and are imaginary ones, similarly to the Schwarzschild case. It seems to indicate the absence of the bound states. Nevertheless, the non-vanishing NUT charge influences the wave characteristics, for example, results in decrease of resonant energies absolute values.

We have demonstrated that the potentials become complex-valued functions at real NUT charge, but, interestingly, they become real-valued at imaginary NUT-charge. The last fact has encouraged us to consider the extremal NUT black hole with a single horizon, when the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy vanishes identically, and reveal the non-zero NUT charge effects in wave characteristics. We have shown that the wave number increases with the rise of the NUT charge.

As a result of analysis of the radial equations for massive particle, it has been demonstrated that similarly to Kerr black hole, the probability of particle–antiparticle production on the outer event horizon decreases for NUT black hole comparing to Schwarzschild case, but the characters of the effects of angular moment (for Kerr black hole) and NUT charge (for NUT black hole) are different.

The results obtained in the paper may distinguish NUT black holes from another type of black holes in the future when the experimental setup will allow such type of observations. But today, there arise the necessity of the following elucidation and explanation of the NUT charge from the physical point of view and finding an appropriate constraints on its values.

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